

Thermal, Infrared and X-Ray Studies on Praseodymium and Neodymium Myristates

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The thermal decomposition of praseodymium and neodymium myristates has been studied both as a function of temperature and of time. The thermogravimetric analysis has shown that order of decomposition reaction is kinetically of zero order and the energy of activation for the decomposition process lies in the range of 10–15 kcal mol⁻¹. The ir results showed that lanthanide myristates have an ionic character. The X-ray analysis indicated that the zigzag chains of the fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules extend straight forward on both sides of each basal plane and the molecular axes of the soap molecules are somewhat inclined to the basal plane.

A survey of literature reveals that the physicochemical studies of alkali, alkaline earth and transition metal soaps have been extensively studied whereas only a few references¹ are available on rare earth metal soaps although these soaps are being widely used in many industries. The present work deals with the studies of thermal, infrared and X-ray analysis of praseodymium and neodymium myristates in order to determine the kinetics of thermal decomposition and structure of these soaps in solid state.

Results and Discussion

Thermogravimetric analysis : The final residues left on heating praseodymium and neodymium myristates were the metal oxides as the amounts of the residues were in agreement with the theoretically calculated ones. A white substance found condensed at the cold part of the sample tube was identified as myristone (m.p. 34°). The thermal decomposition at 660° (Fig. 1) of these soaps can be expressed as

where M stands for praseodymium and neodymium.

Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition of (+) Pr-myristate and (*) Nd-myristate.

The curves of the thermal decomposition of praseodymium and neodymium myristate were explained in the light of various equations. The Freeman-Carroll² rate expression for the thermal decomposition of these soaps, where they disappeared continuously with the constant rate of increase in temperature and with the passage of time and when one of the products being gaseous, can be expressed as

$$\frac{\Delta [\log (dw/dt)]}{\Delta (\log W_r)} = -\frac{E}{2.303R} \cdot \frac{\Delta (1/T)}{\Delta (\log W_r)} + n$$

where E, n, T, W_r and (dw/dt) are respectively energy of activation, order of reaction, temperature on absolute scale, difference between the total loss

in weight and the loss in weight at time t , i.e. $(W_0 - W_t)$, and rates of weight-loss obtained from the loss in weight vs time curves at appropriate times. The values of energy of activation for the decomposition process was calculated from the slope of the plot of $-\Delta[\log(dw/dt)/\Delta(\log W_t)]$ against $\Delta(1/T)/\Delta(\log W_t)$. The order of reaction for the thermal decomposition of praseodymium and neodymium myristates was found zero and the values of energy of activation for the thermal decomposition of these soaps were in the range of 10–15 kcal mol⁻¹. The value of energy of activation for praseodymium myristate (10.2 kcal mol⁻¹) is lower than the value of neodymium myristate (14.7 kcal mol⁻¹).

The aforesaid fact that the process of decomposition of praseodymium and neodymium myristates is kinetically of zero order, is in harmony with the fact that the surface of the soap molecule remains completely covered all the time by the molecules of the gaseous product and so the decomposition is fast and the rate of decomposition becomes constants.

Horowitz and Metzger³ and Coats and Redfern⁴ also provided a method for the evaluation of energy of activation for the thermal decomposition of these soaps. Horowitz and Metzger's equation can be represented as

$$\ln[\ln(1-\alpha)^{-1}] = \frac{E}{RT_s^2} \theta$$

where α , E , T_s and θ are respectively the fraction of the soap decomposed at time t , energy of activation, temperature on absolute scale at which the rate of decomposition is maximum and θ is equivalent to $(T - T_s)$.

The plots of $\ln[\ln(1-\alpha)^{-1}]$ against θ for praseodymium and neodymium soaps are linear. The values of energy of activation obtained from the slope of the curves are 11.5 and 13.2 kcal mol⁻¹ for praseodymium and neodymium myristates respectively.

Coats and Redfern's equation for zero order reaction can be written as

$$\log(\alpha/T^2) = \log \frac{AR}{aE} \left[1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right] - \frac{E}{2.303 RT}$$

where α , T , R , A , a and E are the fraction of the soap decomposed, temperature on absolute scale, gas constant, frequency factor, rate of heating (°C per min) and energy of activation respectively.

It may be pointed out that the plots of $\log(\alpha/T^2)$ against $(1/T)$ are straight lines with slopes equal to $(-E/2.303R)$. The values of energy of activation for praseodymium and neodymium myristates are 13.5 and 15.0 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

The above discussion leads to the conclusion that the thermal decomposition of praseodymium and neodymium myristates is kinetically of zero order and the activation energy for the process lies in the range 10–15 kcal mol⁻¹.

Ir spectra : The ir spectral bands and their tentative assignments for praseodymium and neodymium myristates are assigned and compared with sodium myristate as well as myristic acid (Table 1). The vibrational frequencies which are characteristic of the aliphatic portion of fatty acids do not change when the acid is converted into sodium, praseodymium and neodymium soaps. The myristic acid displays a very broad intense peak due to OH stretching near 2640 cm⁻¹. The appearance of the band near 1700 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of myristic acid reveals that the acid exists as dimer and confirms the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonding between two molecules of myristic acid. One of the characteristic bands of the dimeric carboxylic acid from the out-of-plane bending OH group appears near 940 cm⁻¹. The absorption maxima near 690 and 550 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of myristic acid are due to carboxyl group bending and wagging modes and are dependent on the chain-length of the fatty acid radical.

The infrared spectra of sodium, praseodymium and neodymium myristates show marked differences with the spectra of the corresponding myristic acid in some spectral regions. The characteristic vibrations of free myristic acid were found completely absent in their respective regions in the spectra of these

TABLE 1—IR SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) WITH ASSIGNMENTS OF PRASEODYMIUM AND NEODYMIUM MYRISTATES

Assignment	Myristic acid	Sodium myristate	Praseodymium myristate	Neodymium myristate
CH_3 , C—H asym.	2 960	-	2 960	2 960
CH_2 , C—H asym.	2 920	2 920	2 920	2 920
CH_2 , C—H sym.	2 855	2 840	2 850	2 850
OH	2 640	2 640	-	-
C=O	1 700	-	-	-
COO^- , C—O asym.	-	1 550	1 530	1 530
CH_2 deform	1 465	1 460	1 470	1 470
C—O + O—H in-plane deform.	1 430	1 445	1 460	1 450
COO^- , C—C sym.	-	1 420	1 410	1 415
Progressive bands (CH_2 twist and wag.)	1 350–1 190	1 340–1 100	1 355–1 200	1 360–1 150
CH_3 rocking	1 120–1 065	1 105–1 120	1 110–1 090	1 090–1 020
OH out-of-plane deform.	940	-	-	-
COO^- deform	-	935	940	940
CH_2 rocking	735–725	755–725	720	720
COOH bend	690	700	690–620	680–620
COOH wag	550	580–454	590–570	600–500
M—O	-	-	440	440

metal myristates. The complete disappearance of the carbonyl frequency at $1\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and appearance of two bands corresponding to the symmetric and asymmetric vibrations of carboxylate ion near $1\,410$ – $1\,420$ and $1\,530$ – $1\,550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, in the spectra of sodium, praseodymium and neodymium myristates, indicate that there is a complete resonance in the C—O bonds of carboxyl group of the soap molecules and the two bonds become identical with the force constants assuming the values intermediate between those of the normal double and single bonds. It is, therefore, concluded that the resonance character of the ionised carboxyl group is retained in these metal soaps.

It may be pointed out that the metal-to-oxygen bonds in the ionised structure of praseodymium and neodymium myristates should have an ionic character. However, the bond in praseodymium and neodymium myristates are not purely ionic but partially covalent in character. The band observed at 440 cm^{-1} corresponds to M—O bond in the spectra of praseodymium and neodymium myristates.

In the spectrum of myristic acid, no band corresponding to asymmetric and symmetric vibrations of carboxylate ion is observed. Naturally, the OH

stretching band near $2\,640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and OH deformation band at 940 cm^{-1} observed in the spectrum of myristic acid, disappeared in the spectra of sodium, praseodymium and neodymium myristates. The progressive bands with medium or weak intensity observed at $1\,355$ – $1\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for praseodymium myristate and at $1\,360$ – $1\,150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for neodymium myristate are assigned to the wagging and twisting vibrations of the soap or acid. It may be pointed out that these peaks are weaker in the spectra of the metal soaps than in the spectra of the fatty acids.

The infrared spectra of these metal soaps do not show any absorption maxima in the region $3\,500$ – $3\,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates the absence of any coordinated water molecules in the soaps.

X-ray diffraction : The calculated spacings together with the relative intensities with respect to the most intense peaks are recorded in Table 2. A large number of intense peaks arising from the diffraction of X-rays by planes of praseodymium and neodymium ions (known as basal planes) were recorded over the range 5 – 65° of the diffraction angle in the diffraction patterns of praseodymium and neodymium myristates. The appearance of the

TABLE 2—X-RAY DIFFRACTION ANALYSIS OF PRASEODYMIUM AND NEODYMIUM MYRISTATES

Sl. no.	θ	$\sin \theta$	$\frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta}$	d (Å)	n
Praseodymium myristate .					
1.	3.36	0.058 6	13.16	39.47	3
2	4.47	0.078 0	9.88	39.54	4
3.	5.59	0.097 3	7.92	39.60	5
4.	6.71	0.116 3	6.60	39.59	6
5.	7.83	0.136 3	5.66	39.59	7
6.	8.96	0.155 8	4.95	39.59	8
7.	10.23	0.177 6	4.34	39.06	9
8.	11.21	0.194 4	3.97	39.66	10
9.	12.36	0.214 0	3.60	39.62	11
10.	13.50	0.235 5	3.30	39.62	12
11.	14.65	0.252 9	3.05	39.63	13
12.	16.95	0.291 5	2.64	39.65	15
Average value of d (Å) = 39.55 Å					
Neodymium myristate :					
1	3.35	0.058 4	13.19	39.57	3
2.	4.46	0.078 8	9.91	39.63	4
3.	5.58	0.097 2	7.93	39.67	5
4	6.71	0.116 8	6.60	39.60	6
5.	7.80	0.135 7	5.68	39.77	7
6.	10.09	0.175 1	4.40	39.62	9
7.	11.18	0.1939	3.98	39.77	10
8.	19.61	0.335 6	2.30	39.05	17
9.	26.62	0.448 0	1.72	39.58	23
Average value of d (Å) = 39.58 Å					

integral series upto 15th order for praseodymium and neodymium myristates, suggests good crystallinity for these soaps. The average planer distance for the integral series, i.e. the long spacing for praseodymium myristate and neodymium myristate is 39.55 and 39.58 Å, respectively. The differences between the observed values of long spacing of praseodymium myristate (39.55 Å) and palmitate (44.67 Å) is 5.12 Å which corresponding to double the length of additional methylene group in the fatty acid radical constituent of the soap molecules. The values of the long spacing for these soaps are almost equal to double the length of fatty acid radical of the soap molecules. It is, therefore, suggested that the zigzag chains of the fatty acid radical extend straight forward on both sides of each basal plane.

The results of X-ray diffraction of lanthanide

myristates show that the observed value of long spacing for these soaps (praseodymium myristate, 39.55 and neodymium myristate, 39.58 Å) are smaller than the calculated dimensions of myristate ion (42.0 Å) from Pauling's values of atomic radii and bond angles. This suggests that the molecular axes of praseodymium and neodymium myristates are somewhat inclined to the basal plane and the metal ions fit into spaces between oxygen atoms of the ionised carboxyl group without a large strain of the bonds.

Numerous diffraction peaks in the intermediate range of the diffraction angles are also observed in the diffraction patterns of praseodymium and neodymium myristates and these are attributed to the diffraction of X-ray by planes of atoms of much smaller separation than basal planes. The calculated spacings from these peaks correspond

to the shorter side spacings, i.e. the lateral distance between one soap molecule and the next in a layer. It is observed that the long spacing peaks are fairly intense while the short spacing peaks are relatively weak.

On the basis of long and short spacings, it is proposed the metal ions in praseodymium and neodymium myristates are arranged in a parallel plane, i.e. a basal plane equally spaced in the soap crystal with fully extended zigzag chains of fatty acid radicals on both sides of each basal plane and these soaps have double layer structure as proposed by Vold and Hattiangdi⁵.

Conclusion :

The decomposition of synthetic praseodymium and neodymium myristates results in the formation of ketone and metal oxide and kinetically it was found to be of zero order. Activation energy for the decomposition lies in the range 10–15 kcal mol⁻¹. Structural analysis confirmed the existence of hydrogen bonding between the carboxyl group and slight inclination of molecular axes to the basal plane.

Experimental

All the chemical were use of AnalaR grade. Praseodymium and neodymium myristates were prepared by the direct precipitation of sodium myristate with the required amount of the aqueous solutions of praseodymium and neodymium nitrates at 50–55° under vigorous stirring. The precipitated soaps were washed with double-distilled water and acetone to remove the excess of metal ions and unreacted myristic acid. The purity of these soaps was checked by the elemental analysis and the results were found in agreement with the theoretically calculated values. The reproducibility of the results was checked by preparing two sample of the same soap under similar conditions.

The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out at a constant rate of heating (15° min⁻¹) in a thermobalance (Mettler TG 50) in the atmosphere

of nitrogen. The infrared spectra (KBr) were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The powder X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained with a Philips PW-1730 diffractometer using Cu-K_α radiations filtered by a nickel foil over the range of diffraction angle. $2\theta = 5-65^\circ$, where θ is the Bragg's angle.

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